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The language of Parliament

What work of Australian political history contains almost 500 million words contributed by over a thousand different authors?

Hansard is the record of what was spoken in the Commonwealth Parliament from 1901 to the present. Debates, speeches, questions, even interjections – it's all recorded in Hansard.

You can search Hansard using the [ParlInfo database](#), and explore recent years on the [Open Australia](#) site. But I'm particularly interested in what we might learn from the historic content.

Pre-digital editions of Hansard have been through a process known as Optical Character Recognitions (OCR) to make the printed text available in electronic form. Within each file, the various parts that make up a sitting day in Parliament – like debates and questions – are clearly marked. This makes it easier to search the text, but it also means we can explore the *language* of Hansard in different ways.

We're used to searching for particular documents within a collection, but what about searching for particular words or phrases *across* a collection – tracking their use, context, and variations through time. You can try this for yourself on the Museum's [Election Speeches](#) site. There you can visualise the frequency of words across 89 election policy speeches.

Hansard is a **lot** bigger, containing something like 300,000 speeches and 150,000 questions. The first step is just getting all the text files together in a form that can be analysed. Last year I [wrote a computer script](#) to download all of Hansard from 1901 to 1980 from the ParlInfo database. There's 9,829 files, one for every sitting day in the House of Representatives and the Senate. I've saved them in a [GitHub repository](#) where anyone can easily grab their own copies.

Using these files I created [Historic Hansard](#), a website dedicated to 'lovers of political speech'. While ParlInfo is good for searching, Historic Hansard is meant for reading. Each day's proceedings is presented on a single page, giving you a sense of the rhythm, flow, and structure of the day. But there's a few added extras. A [bill index](#) makes it easy to track the historical development of legislation, while a [people index](#) lists the contributions of each individual member.

The screenshot shows the top navigation bar of the Historic Hansard website. It includes the site name "Historic Hansard", dropdown menus for "House of Reps" and "Senate", and an "About" link. A search bar with a magnifying glass icon is on the right. Below the navigation is the main heading "IMMIGRATION RESTRICTION BILL". A list of dates follows, representing various readings of the bill:

- [5 June 1901](#)
- [7 August 1901](#) (Second Reading)
- [6 September 1901](#) (Second Reading)
- [12 September 1901](#) (Second Reading)
- [20 September 1901](#)
- [25 September 1901](#)
- [26 September 1901](#)
- [27 September 1901](#)
- [1 October 1901](#)
- [1 October 1901](#)
- [3 October 1901](#)
- [3 October 1901](#)
- [4 October 1901](#)
- [8 October 1901](#) (Third Reading)
- [9 October 1901](#) (Third Reading)
- [11 December 1901](#)
- [12 December 1901](#)
- [6 December 1905](#) (Second Reading)
- [14 December 1905](#)
- [3 December 1908](#)
- [7 December 1908](#)
- [10 December 1908](#) (Second Reading)
- [11 December 1908](#)
- [1 July 1910](#)
- [27 July 1910](#)

Tracking the history of the Immigration Restriction Act using Historic Hansard's bill index. Image: Tim Sherratt

But we can do more. Historic Hansard also provides some examples of what becomes possible when we make historical resources available in digital form. The site integrates [Hypothes.is](#), a web-scale annotation tool. This means that anyone can enrich the content with notes, links, comments, and images. Imagine a [classroom project](#) where students annotate a year of Hansard with information about all the people, places, and events mentioned in Parliament.

Pages for each day and year in Historic Hansard also include a 'View in Voyant' button. This opens the text in [Voyant Tools](#), a web-based text analysis workbench. Voyant treats text as data, enabling you to analyse the frequency, distribution, and context of individual words within those many thousands of speeches. A wide range of [tools and](#)

[visualisations](#) are built in to Voyant, and you can easily embed the results in your own web site. If Voyant gets you hooked on the possibilities of text analysis, you can take things further by downloading multiple days or years from my [Hansard repository](#) and manually importing them into Voyant or another text analysis tool like [AntConc](#).

Voyant Tools ?				
Contexts ?				
Document	Left	Term	Right	
4)	advocate the free entry of	chinese	into Australia ? I cannot understand	
4)	labourers ; there are also the	chinese	. 179 F4S PARRAMATTA, NEW SOUTH	
4)	and that employers of Japanese,	chinese	, Javanese, Hindoos, Afghans, and the	
4)	advocate the free entry of	chinese	into Australia ? I cannot understand	
4)	much more vital, connected with	chinese	or the Afghans or Hindoos	
5)	face the trouble of a	chinese	invasion, and some steps must	
of the black race problem of the United States. It is a problem which has troubled the greatest statesmen and publicists in that country. Already in the Northern Territory the Minister for Trades and Customs, in conjunction with Sir Horace Tozer, of Queensland, has had to face the trouble of a Chinese invasion, and some steps must be taken to avert in Australia the evils which have caused such great difficulties in the United States of America. There should be no want of courage displayed in dealing with this matter. Although the leader of the Opposition and the leader of the Government				
5)	Bill for the restriction of	chinese	immigration ; but it was vetoed	
5)	Bill for the restriction of	chinese	; it was a Bill to	
5)	the present New South Wales	chinese	Restriction Act, many years before	
5)	a Bill to amend the	chinese	Restriction Act, which imposes a	
5)	tax of £100 on every	chinese	entering the State of New	
5)	our northern shores Indians and	chinese	, and these black and yellow	
5)	and in customs with the	chinese	; but, for reasons which I	
5)	and less protective than the	chinese	policy. The direct outcome of	
6)	But there are Japanese, Javanese,	chinese	, and Hindoos, who not only	
7)	to the tremendous influx of	chinese	into Port Darwin at the	
7)	labour, which meant, of course,	chinese	labour, and they had introduced	
7)	had introduced' 6,000 .or 7,000	chinese	to do the work, so	

Using Voyant to explore the context of the keyword "Chinese" in House of Representatives Hansard from 1901. Image: Tim Sherratt

Hansard is a rich resource for exploration and research, but something is lost when the spoken word is transcribed into text. Are there ways in which we might use Hansard to recover some of the theatre, drama, humour, and personality of Parliament?

Amongst the more formal speeches and statements, Hansard records interjections – short comments or questions from across the chamber that interrupt the current speaker. Almost [a million interjections](#) from 1901 to 1980 are included in Hansard. Recently, as I was fiddling around with ways of displaying them, I started to see the interjections as something akin to tweets – quick, pithy, and pointed. What would happen, I wondered, if we reimagined interjections from a century ago in an age of social media.

[Real Words :: Imagined Tweets](#) displays randomly selected interjections as if they were tweets. The words, speakers, and dates are real. The Twitter handles, activity stats,

and times are invented. As the 'tweets' load, conversations build up across the decades. You can filter the interjections using keywords, and you might even spot an emoji or two!

George Pearce

@SenatorPearce

We very largely owe the white Australia policy to Sir Henry Parkes. historichansard.net/sena

3:13 AM - 8 Oct 1903

2

20

45

William Story

@SenatorStory

It is the people who believe in a White Australia. historichansard.net/sena

4:16 PM - 1 Apr 1908

2

23

52

Patrick Lynch

@SenatorLynch

I would not have gone there and have turned my back on the White Australia policy as the Labour party did. historichansard.net/sena

10:36 PM - 8 Mar 1929

8

19

2

Interjections including the phrase “White Australia” reimagined as tweets. Image: Tim Sherratt

Instead of shelf after shelf of bound volumes of Hansard, we now have 500 million words, spoken by our elected representatives, available in digital form. Topics can be analysed, aggregated, tracked, and visualised. Contexts can be enriched and extended. We’ve only just started to explore these possibilities. Think about the new questions you can ask, the patterns you can find, the perspectives you can build. By learning the language of Parliament we can find new ways of understanding our political past.

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Canberra. Tim’s tools and experiments include important things like [The Real Face of White Australia](#), useful things like [QueryPic](#), and strange things like [The Vintage Face Depot](#). You can find him at timsherratt.org or as [@wragge](#) on Twitter.